

Quora is Crap Thread

After I documented the following page of fascist Big Tech censorship, I decided to keep a running tabulation of examples of academic, pseudo-intellectual, leftist drivel on Quora's obvious echo chamber. It's worse now than NPR or MSNBC. It's full of dictatorial propaganda pretending to be intelligent.

1/13/22 First up, ye old "steel man" routine.

2

1/13/22 First up, ye old “steel man” routine.

[Mats Andersson](#)

Has a functioning brain, at least when he's had coffee [Dec 9](#)

[Is Joe Biden a communist?](#)

There's a sort of litmus test you can apply.

- Has he nationalised all factories and corporations so that all means of production are controlled by the workers?
- Has he abolished banks?
- Has he abolished religion?
- Has he abolished working for money instead of for whatever actual *items* you need?
- Has he abolished national borders?
- Has he abolished the Army?
- Has he abolished the individual states and replaced them with worker councils?
- Has he abolished the Federal Government?

- Has he even ever advocated for any of the above?

If the answer is “Yes” to at least a handful of the above, then it might be justified to call him a Communist.

If the answer is “No” to all of the above, then he hasn't done even the most basic things people need to do to qualify as “Communist”.

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6.2K

18

485

Adding comments disabled

[Charles Lyell](#) · December 23

If only there were enough on the right capable of grasping the point. If they knew how to think they'd change sides. Their idea of logic is, “All grass is green, this object is green, therefore it must be grass.”

[Diane Grant](#) · December 25

Yes, it seems they more or less affirm the consequent: Communists are bad, [Trump & FOX News constantly tell me that Biden is bad, therefore, he must be a Communist.](#) Or maybe: I heard that Bernie is a democratic socialist, therefore I believe that all Democrats are communists. Because those two things...

[\(more\)](#)

[Rene Christensen](#) Ignorance can be excused. True stupidity is a tragedy. Most of them are willfully ignorant of facts, intellectually lazy. They have no excuse.

Greg Masucci · December 31

I agree, but I think it is a little more like this:

All grass is green, but that grass over there is dark green AND doesn't think exactly like me, so it's not REALLY grass at all. In fact, it must be a communist or a socialist, I can't remember which is which, but they're definitely some "bad hombres"!

Kenneth FaulkIn government as is life not everything is either black or white. There are shades of gray in between. For some simple minded Americans, however, that is often too hard to grasp.

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Eli Elyzium · Sun

Calling Biden a Communist is, and has always been a political weapon used to gain the support of the ignorant and gullible segment of the population.

As the author noted, it's never been rooted in facts. It's true fake news and propaganda at play to call Biden either a communist, or a socialist.

Ed Hecht · 17h ago

"...to gain the support of the ignorant and gullible segment of the population."

Sadly this segment is close to 50% of the populace. Amazing how these high functioning cretins throw around the labels, communist, socialist and/or fascist and have ZERO understanding what they mean.

Joe AbbottI have literally seen Jordan Klepper confront a woman who claimed

I doubt very much that this was a sincere question, to begin with. No one serious on the right says Joe Biden (Brandon) is a communist. He's a racist¹², a potential pedosexual^{3 4}, a harasser of women⁵, probably a sexual abuser⁶, has dementia^{7 8}, and a kleptocrat⁹. He's definitely enjoying fascist power¹⁰ from COVID, but all

¹ <https://www.cnn.com/2020/05/22/politics/biden-charlamagne-tha-god-you-aint-black/index.html>

² As is the LA Times, apparently, <https://www.latimes.com/opinion/story/2020-05-22/biden-says-if-youre-black-and-dont-vote-for-him-youre-not-black-hes-right>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ovA9UXJvGeI>

⁴

<https://www.redvoicemedia.com/2021/11/biden-incest-and-pedophilia-confirmed-ashley-bidens-diary-legitimate-fbi-cover-up-exposed/>

⁵ https://www.huffpost.com/entry/joe-biden-sexual-assault-tara-reade_n_5e7e69c8c5b6256a7a2a88f2

⁶ <https://www.businessinsider.com/joe-biden-allegations-women-2020-campaign-2019-6?op=1>

⁷ <https://nypost.com/2021/11/21/white-house-doctor-is-hiding-joe-bidens-brain-drain-devine/>

⁸ <https://teaparty.org/obama-rages-after-former-white-house-doctor-exposes-bidens-dementia-471623/>

⁹ klep·toc·ra·cy | \ klep- 'tä-krə-sē \ plural kleptocracies

Definition of kleptocracy: government by those who seek chiefly status and personal gain at the expense of the governed

<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/kleptocracy>

¹⁰ fas·cism | \ 'fa-,shi-zəm also 'fa-,si- \

Definition of fascism <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/fascism>

1 often capitalized : a political philosophy, movement, or regime (such as that of the Fascisti) that exalts nation and often race above the individual and that stands for a centralized [autocratic](#) government headed by a [dictatorial](#) leader, severe economic and social regimentation, and forcible suppression of opposition

2: a tendency toward or actual exercise of strong autocratic or dictatorial control

oligarchs¹¹ do. The kompromat¹² on his family makes him unsuitable for office, much less the Presidency. But creating a false argument to slam dunk on is the literal definition of patheticville in intellectual debate. The fact that all the answers/replies align up and then proceed to “slam dunk” on Republicans and/or Fox is made all the more ironic by how out of touch and self-unaware they are.

Responding to the moronic above, in highlighted order:

1. Displaying obvious favoritism and sarcastic, even sardonic¹³ detest.
2. The irony of saying this, with a straight face, after ~~four~~ six (6) years of Trump bashing is the height of confirmation bias¹⁴.
3. Pot, meet kettle.
4. Again, the difference here is the group you’re attacking have always supported the flag, the Constitution, the complete Bill of Rights¹⁵, etc. Whereas you’re supporting social deconstructionists, and are what Yuri Bezmenov said blatantly¹⁶, is termed by Communists as “Useful Idiots.”¹⁷
5. Ah, the old straw man¹⁸. With ad hominem¹⁹ no less. They are throwing around labels, those “cretins!” I think it is more likely that the red voters know exactly what they were told by the WW1, WW2, Korean and Vietnam veteran generations what communism, socialism, and fascism are, why we fought them, and *your side* has been playing Orwellian games and changing the definitions of terms (like racism²⁰). Let’s play Occam’s Razor²¹. What seems more plausible... a man who was beloved by the Clintons,

¹¹ ol-i-gar-chy | \ 'ä-lə- gär-kē , 'ō- \ plural oligarchies

1: government by the few

The corporation is ruled by oligarchy.

2: a government in which a small group exercises control especially for corrupt and selfish purposes

a military oligarchy was established in the country

also : a group exercising such control

An oligarchy ruled the nation.

3: an organization under [oligarchic](https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/oligarchy) control <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/oligarchy>

Essentially as Biden’s collusion with the media demonstrates, if they can shut out dissent and establish rule by media and select Democratic insiders, this fits all the above definitions.

¹²

¹³ grimly mocking or cynical.

"Starkey attempted a sardonic smile"

¹⁴

<https://www.breitbart.com/politics/2021/08/11/hunter-biden-says-he-lost-another-laptop-to-russian-drug-dealers-in-naked-pillow-talk/>

¹⁵ While your side is not supporting half the Bill of Rights and cannot be considered liberal.

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bX3EZCVj2XA>

¹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yErKTVdETpw>

¹⁸ Definition of straw man <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/straw%20man>

1: a weak or imaginary opposition (such as an argument or adversary) set up only to be easily confuted

2: a person set up to serve as a cover for a usually questionable transaction

¹⁹ ad ho-mi-nem | \ (') ad- 'hä-mə-,nem , -nem \ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/ad%20hominem>

Definition of ad hominem (Entry 1 of 2)

1: appealing to feelings or prejudices rather than intellect

an ad hominem argument

2: marked by or being an attack on an opponent's character rather than by an answer to the contentions made made an ad hominem personal attack on his rival

²⁰

<https://www.goodmorningamerica.com/living/story/merriam-webster-redefining-racism-college-graduate-calls-action-71193936>

²¹ Oc-cam's razor | \ 'ä-kəmz- \ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/Occam's%20razor>

variants: or less commonly [Ockham's razor](https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/Ockham's%20razor)

Definition of Occam's razor: a scientific and philosophical rule that entities should not be multiplied unnecessarily which is interpreted as requiring that the simplest of competing theories be preferred to the more complex or that explanations of unknown phenomena be sought first in terms of known quantities

Snoop Dogg, and Chuck Schumer until he left the Democratic Party was a secret Russia loving Klan member **OR** Hillary Clinton used the “berate the mulberry tree”²² stratagem to hide her own factual Russian Collusion²³ (Steele Dossier)²⁴ and the DNC coverup, email scandal, Obama’s own scandals, as well as the never-been-debunked²⁵ Wikileaks²⁶ which exposed the behaviors of the elite Democrats and RINOs? Who had more to gain, and who more to lose?

Trump lost over a \$billion in net worth.²⁷ What has the Biden organization had to gain through paying for factual election theft and then what have Orwellian Big Tech/Brother companies had to gain by conspiring to cover it up and make it censorable to discuss it?²⁸ If they did this to the COVID lab theory²⁹, gain-of-function^{30 31} and Kyle Rittenhouse³², etc. and had to later recant their unfactual “fact checking” ... might they also do the same with the Biden family? 2+2=?

If he has factual seeming accusers^{33 34} for rape and abuse, who never get a court day³⁵ or even media heyday, and he can make overtly racist statements³⁶ that never go fully challenged³⁷... who is the one seeming more and more like Hitler?

Again, that these people above believe themselves to be intelligent is more a sign about why the West has an Average IQ of only 99³⁸, than it says anything about Trump or Republicans. Quora is Crap, and it is agendized crap. This is called *Normalization* of the process called *Demoralization*.

22

https://military-history.fandom.com/wiki/Thirty_Six_Stratagems#Point_at_the_mulberry_tree_while_cursing_the_locust_tree

23 <https://nypost.com/2021/11/05/inside-the-clinton-dossier-and-the-con-behind-the-russiagate-scandal/>

24

<https://www.investors.com/politics/editorials/memo-fbi-used-tainted-steele-dossier-paid-for-by-hillary-clinton-as-reason-to-spy-on-trump/>

25 <https://caityjohnstone.medium.com/hillary-clinton-just-told-five-blatant-lies-about-wikileaks-f463d66b63ef>

26 <https://wikileaks.org/clinton-emails/>

27 <https://www.foxbusiness.com/politics/donald-trump-net-worth-presidency>

28

<https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/opinion/why-big-tech-censored-our-podcast-touching-on-2020-election-irregularities-opinion/ar-BB1f9JhC>

29 <https://news.yahoo.com/bill-maher-blasts-big-tech-183200440.html>

30 <https://headlineusa.com/gop-shame-censoring-covid-organ/>

31

<https://nypost.com/2021/10/21/faucis-agency-admits-it-funded-gain-of-function-work-in-wuhan-what-else-are-they-keeping-from-us/>

32 <https://www.foxnews.com/opinion/tucker-carlson-media-big-tech-kyle-rittenhouse>

33 <https://punchingbagpost.com/underage-victim-accuses-joe-biden-of-sexual-assault/>

34 Biden himself on The View “That happened over 20 years ago”

35 <https://nypost.com/2021/03/15/biden-gets-away-with-exactly-what-cuomo-is-accused-of/>

36 “Poor kids just as smart as white kids” and

<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/leahbarkoukis/2021/06/02/bidens-comments-about-black-entrepreneurs-n2590342> etc.

The fact that I can sue etc. is enough said.

37 <https://www.heritage.org/progressivism/commentary/bidens-history-getting-away-racist-remarks>

38 (98 (US) + 100 (EU))/2 = 99